

Design of thermoplastic tanks for thermal energy storage applications using Finite Element Analysis

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ABSTRACT

In this work, results from the design and development of thermal energy storage (TES) tanks targeted for thermal energy storage applications, using Finite Element Analysis (FEA), are presented and discussed. The tanks are a part of the innovative Tesse2b solution, a modular and low-cost thermal storage technology, based on solar collectors, and highly efficient heat pumps, for heating, cooling and domestic hot water production. The TES tanks contain a heat exchanger (HE) and the paraffin phase change material (PCM), required for the thermal storage, which is selected depending on the targeted application. They also comprise insulation to prevent thermal losses. The tanks' shape is cuboid and they are made of a thermoplastic material, which was selected after extensive testing and due to better thermal properties. The material selected is polypropylene a material with long term working temperature approx. 90oC.

The target was to design paraffin TES tanks in a compact and modular manner taking into account easy scaling of the system to meet thermal energy needs of residential buildings with various sizes and for different climates. The tank design process took into account material compatibility, operating temperatures and expected load from content considering a design life. The design of the paraffin TES tanks was performed in compliance with the EN12573 standard for reinforced and non-reinforced tanks. The mechanical properties of the tank material (permissible stresses, etc.) were extracted from the standard EN 1778: 2000. Depending on the number of reinforcements used, tanks with different wall thickness were considered. The more reinforcements used the less wall thickness was required. As the service life of thermoplastic tanks depends on creep deformations, to simulate the effect of creep in the TES tanks, a long-term young modulus was used alongside with the normal young modulus, a common approach used in the plastic tanks industry. The designs used for the TES tanks, were verified using FEA structural analysis, to check and visualize the loads and deformations on the tanks. A FEA heat transfer analysis was also conducted to study the insulation and to visualize thermal losses. Due to the needs arising from the use of the tank (thermal energy storage) the thermal analysis is very important for the proper function of the tank. The final tank geometry incorporates one ST-37 Rim on the top of the tank, two ST-37 Ribs and five modulations as proposed by the manufacturer.

INTRODUCTION

Thermal energy storage can serve as critical part in installations working with renewable energy sources (as solar or geothermal energy) supporting to overcome the dependence on weather conditions and the mismatch between energy demand and supply [1-4]. It leads to saving of fuels and primary energy and makes energy systems more cost effective by reducing the energy consumption and capital cost. Such solutions have been studied in IEA SHC Task 42 [5]. It is realized that a compact and modular energy storage unit is required to be integrated in heating

and cooling systems, for their improvement, while the most attractive solution is latent heat storage tanks due to their high energy storage density [1-5]. In TESse2b project [6] a solution targeting residential buildings has been developed that incorporates TES technology. The developed technology is based on solar collectors and highly efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and domestic hot water (DHW) production. It comprises of solar thermal collectors, a geothermal heat pump with vertical Borehole Heat Exchangers, the TESse2b TES tanks which contain the heat exchangers immersed inside the PCM, and additional components as circulating pumps, control valves and the necessary sensors for control and monitoring. Each tank is filled with the appropriate PCMs of different working temperatures, targeting the efficient coverage of DHW, space heating and cooling needs. The hot thermal energy storage tank (HTES) tank will store energy between 38-45°C that can be used for the heating system. The DHW TES tank will store energy between 50-60°C. The cold thermal energy storage tank (CTES), will store energy between 10-17°C and can be used for cooling applications. It was a prerequisite that the tanks should have a modular design so as to permit easy sizing and scaling of the system to meet thermal energy needs of residential buildings with various sizes and for different climates.

When designing TES tanks, different aspects need to be considered such as, technical constraints, cost effectiveness and environmental impact. The design is a complicated task that should take into account various issues including the selection of the tank material, tank shape, the manufacturing method and the correct dimensioning. Compact latent heat storage units, can be polymer-based as they can be easily manufactured with low cost. Thermoplastics are used for many years and applications for storing materials [7], as they usually show sufficient corrosion resistance for a wide range of liquids at ambient temperatures and are less prone to catastrophic failure. They usually have a competitive price and they present a good balance of physico-chemical properties against their dimensional instability under prolonged load. However, they usually require a much thicker construction than metals, which limits the size of tank that can be fabricated. Today, tanks should have been manufactured to the requirements of an appropriate standard [8]. Although in metal tanks their lifetime is determined by the permissible loss of wall thickness in thermoplastic tanks creep deformations are used as design basis for their service life [7-10]. The two main standards DVS-2205 [9] and EN-12573 [10] take into account among others creep for the design of thermoplastic tanks. In cases of new thermoplastic materials, the characteristic properties such as creep strength, creep modulus, etc. are not easily available although their values are required for the tanks design.

In this work, the approach followed to design the Tesse2b TES tanks is presented and discussed. The concept design was based on the existing standards requirements and it was verified using Finite Element structural analysis, to check and visualize the loads and deformations on the tanks. Finally, a FEA heat transfer analysis was conducted to study the insulation and to visualize thermal losses. The use of FEA allows an integrated design, as it focuses on points that may influence the behaviour of the tanks' structure, and affect their structural integrity. The tanks which were finally constructed and were tested at laboratory level, showed the expected behavior [11-12] and that they meet the requirements of the target applications.

DESIGN OF TES TANKS

General approach

The tank design procedure is required to take into account a tank material that can sustain the operating temperatures, usual container placement of stock building spaces for easy integration, compatibility with PCMs, insulation for minimum thermal losses, safety according to standards and must also define a tank design life. Regarding tank material the main options were the high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and the polypropylene (PP) due to their low thermal conductivity, low weight, easy manufacture-easy shaping, low cost and that they are

recyclable. In the design process of such systems it is important to consider except heat transfer issues the compatibility of the tank material with the containing organic PCM especially for the HTES and DHW applications. In a recent work, it was found that both are affected after being in warm contact with the organic PCM tested [13]. For that purpose, a compatibility study was conducted assisting the decision for tank material. Subsequently, considering a cuboid tank shape that matches with the Tesse2b requirements (Figure 1), the design procedure of the tanks was to investigate in accordance with EN12573 standard, and to verify and optimize using Finite Element Analysis (FEA). Based on the market inquiries and the fact that molded tanks are easier to promote in the market, it was decided to proceed with molding as manufacturing method. Due to lack of standards for non-welding tanks, the design was based on standards EN 12573-3: 2000 [10] and EN 1778:1999 [14] which although they refer to welding tanks, in the calculations use a welding factor, that when is equal to 1 represents non-welded (molded) tanks. Design calculations for components are based on long-term values and there are criteria to evaluate as stress and deformation (e.g. deflection). In terms of deformation and stresses, the critical design parameter is Young modulus. The tanks can be strengthened by applying on the outside ribs or frames made of the same or other materials.

Figure 1 Initial tank shape.

Compatibility study

An experimental study was conducted [13] immersing HDPE and PP samples inside organic PCM for a period as stated in ISO 175:1999 [15] which describes a method of exposing test plastic materials specimens to liquid chemicals. In addition, properties determination methods from such immersion are specified. Specimens were immersed in four commercially available PCMs (A44, A46, A54, A58) and kept for a period up to 40 days at $70 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Specimens were removed on specific checkpoint dates i.e. Day 7, Day 28, Day 40 and their properties were measured and recorded. A significant mass uptake was measured for all sample and PCMs even after a short period in contact of polymer with PCMs. As found both HDPE and PP are affected after being in warm contact (70°C) with the organic PCM tested. An epoxy-based resin was suggested as protective coating as no effect occurred on the hardness properties and mass uptake of samples using it. HDPE has lower long-term working temperature, but it is most promising on its mechanical strength. However, as PP has better thermal behavior according to specification (long term working temperature approx. 90°C) it was finally selected, coated with the epoxy resin as the best option.

Concept TES tanks design using standards

Although EN 12573-3: 2000 concerns welded tanks, it uses a corresponding welding factor (f_i) that relates particularly to the welds used to fabricate the tank; for non-welding tank -as it concerns with the Tesse2b molded tanks- it is normal to use a factor of 1 when calculating wall thickness. A non-welded rectangular tank from PP of suitable skin thickness will be designed, so that the maximum deflection (f) of the surfaces (panels) would be within the limits defined by the standard. That is, the maximum deflection (f) shall not be larger than the half skin thickness (t): $f \leq 0,5 t$.

The mechanical properties of the candidate plastics (permissible stresses, etc.) are extracted from the standard

EN 1778 2000 [14]. Many cases were studied, however, in the following typical results are presented for the case of the material selected for the development of the tanks, namely PP. Calculations were made for reinforced and non-reinforced tanks. In each case, the minimum allowable skin thickness (t_{\min}) was calculated, as well as the surface inertia moment (J) of the reinforcements. The value of the inertia moment, calculated by the standard, is such that the deflection of the reinforcements (f) does not exceed 1% of the bottom panel depth. From the moment of inertia (J), the appropriate reinforcement (type - cross-sectional dimensions) is selected. The surface inertia moment (J) was calculated for two cases: for reinforcements formed in the tank by the same material (PP) and for steel reinforcement St-37.

Cases studied. Many cases were studied, however, in the following typical results will be presented for:

- Case 1. Unstiffened tank
- Case 2. Tank with rim stiffening
- Case 3. Tank with rim stiffening and an intermediate horizontal stiffener
- Case 4. Tank with rim stiffening and two intermediate horizontal stiffeners
- Case 5. Tank with rim stiffening and three intermediate horizontal stiffeners

FEA Design

The TES tanks contain the heat exchanger and the PCM required for the thermal energy storage. They are surrounded by insulation to prevent thermal losses and the insulated plastic tanks are placed inside metal containers. The need for a uniform insulation led to place two steel feet beneath the bottom surface of the tank. That configuration changed the area where the maximum deformation occurred. The internal dimensions of the tanks are dictated mainly by the dimensions of the HE and are consistent in all designs studied, leading to the final design. The requirement for modulations that was proposed by the tank manufacturers was adopted concluding to the final tank design.

Structural analysis

Governing Equations-Initial and Boundary conditions. The equations of equilibrium (static or dynamic), conditions of compatibility between strains and displacements, and stress-strain relations or material constitutive law should be satisfied [16]. The initial and boundary conditions on forces and displacements are also included. From consideration of equilibrium equations, one can relate the stresses inside a body to external excitations, including body and surface forces. In the present analysis the loads acting on the tank are the hydrostatic pressure from the liquid PCM to the walls of the tank and the weight of the heat exchanger acting on the bottom of the tank. A fixed support is applied on the bottom of the tank on the surface of the two steel feet. The hydrostatic pressure boundary condition is set in the internal faces of the plastic tank. For the paraffin tanks liquid density equal to 790 kg/m^3 , as this is the highest value for density for all liquid paraffin PCMs: A44, A46 for HTES tank, A53, A58H for DHW tank and A9, A14 for CTES tank (Table 1) considering it as the worst-case scenario. The volume of the liquid PCM inside the tank is about 200 lt.

Grid independence study. For each of the tanks geometries designed, the results obtained were compared to coarser and denser meshes to ensure the grid independency. Due to the different geometries, the number of nodes/elements found in the different designs tested, changes. For each developed mesh a coarser and a finer mesh is constructed in order to compare the accuracy of the results. The correct mesh, from a numerical accuracy standpoint, is one that yields no significant differences in the results when a mesh refinement is introduced. In the present analysis a fine mesh is used the same for both structural and thermal analysis.

Table 1. Thermal and Physical properties of paraffins used in the simulations [17].

Parrafin	A44	A46	A53	A58H	A9	A14
Freezing (Solidification) point (°C)	43.85	45.85	51.05	55.85	7.85	13.65
Melting point (°C)	45.35	46.85	52.45	57.25	8.85	13.85
Density solid (kg/m ³)	912	861	839	816	830	830
Density liquid (kg/m ³)	754	740	772	790	775	775
Thermal conductivity solid (W/mK)	0.24	0.24	0.22	0.22	0.24	0.24
Thermal conductivity liquid (W/mK)	0.24	0.24	0.22	0.22	0.24	0.24
Specific heat solid(kJ/kgK)	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4
Specific heat liquid(kJ/kgK)	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8

For the final tank design, with all its components (rim, ribs, feet, insulation, and cover) the mesh used has 1423162 nodes and 737636 elements. The grid independence study was conducted considering 1001887 nodes and 561939 elements for the coarser mesh and 2100562 nodes and 987823 for the finer mesh. For all the designs leading to the final design, the same procedure was performed. All the meshes used in the analysis were developed using the ANSYS Meshing tool [16].

Tank material properties. The material properties required for linear static structural analyses are density, Young Modulus, and Poisson’s ratio. Material input is handled in Ansys in the “Engineering Data” application [16]. The materials selected for the construction are the PP for the tank and the lid and St-37 steel for the rim and ribs and feet. Other materials such as the polyurethane insulation and the metal cover are used in the assembly but there are not included for the structural analysis. To simulate the effect of creep on the plastic tank a long-term young modulus is used instead of the normal young modulus. The long term (10 years) young modulus is equal to the normal young modulus divided by 4, according to a common approach used in the plastic tanks industry [18]. The properties for the PP are taken after reviewing the literature concerning the PP and properties of the St-37 are taken from the Ansys library [16].

Table 2. Material properties for TES Tanks used in structural analysis [16].

Material Properties				
	Density [Kg/m ³]	Young Modulus [MPa]	Long Term Young Modulus [MPa]	Poisson Ratio
PP	910	1100	275	0.42
St37	7850	2*10 ⁸	---	0.3

Thermal analysis

The goal of the thermal analysis is to insulate the tank for minimum thermal losses and to visualize the heat transfer through the tank. The final design yielded from the structural analysis for each type of PCM was applied, in order to find the insulation needed to have minimum difference from the ambient temperature on the tank surface. Due to the needs arising from the use of the tank -thermal energy storage- the thermal analysis is very important for the proper function of the tank. The analysis was made for all three applications (CTES, HTES, DHW) by implementing different PCM temperatures, as temperature loads. For each application the worst-case scenario was

considered and the thermal loads for the HTES and DHW tanks are the highest values that the PCM faces during the experiment while for the CTES tank is the lowest temperature. Further to model different environmental conditions two different ambient temperatures were used. The geometry and the computational grid used in the thermal analysis of the tank is the same as for the structural analysis. The governing partial differential heat conduction equation in three dimensions for the temperature was solved for steady state conditions [16]. The thermal analysis of the system was conducted for boundary conditions in consistency with the experimental conditions [6,11,12]. In order to test the worst-case scenario for the tanks, the highest, lowest and a mid-state temperature observed in the tank during operation, are set as the constant internal temperatures of tank successively. For each of these temperatures two different temperatures are set as the ambient temperature of the environment. The two ambient temperatures one is low and one high to simulate typical weather condition for winter and summer. Additionally, a convection coefficient is applied to the external faces of the tank according to each ambient temperature.

Table 2. Material properties for TES Tanks used for thermal analysis [16].

	Density [kg/m ³]	Thermal Conductivity [W/m°C]	Specific Heat [J/Kg°C]
St-37	7850	60.5	434
Polypropylene	910	0.22	1920
Polyurethane	16.019	0.024	1800

The PCM temperature inside the tank was set as the temperature load, the room temperatures when the experiments were conducted, are set as the ambient temperatures, and the convection coefficient were taken by Ansys model for stagnant air [16].

TYPICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Standard analysis. Considering the above five cases, it was concluded that the Case 4 (Figure 2) namely tank with rim stiffening and two intermediate horizontal stiffeners, and wall thickness 9 mm covers the limits required by the standard. For Cases 1-3 and in order to assure a safe construction that can withstand the loads, the tank surface thickness should be more than 10 mm, which will result in expensive construction. For Case 5, with a thickness of 6 mm, the construction cost of the tank is similar to that for Case 4, with a thickness of 10 mm, but requires more reinforcement, which will increase the cost and the weight of the tank. In all cases it was not possible to use reinforcements formed by the same material (polypropylene PP), since the inertia moment for the use of it as reinforcement has such a large numerical value that it made it impossible to select an appropriate profile from this material.

Figure 2 Drawing of the tank with rim stiffening and two intermediate horizontal stiffeners.

From the standard analysis, taking into account the weight of the tank and the deformations appearing on its surface, it was concluded that Cases 3,4,5 are the most suitable for Tesse2b application based on the weight and the deformation observed. As for Case 3 the weight is higher and in Case 5 the simulation with long term young modulus yielded results that are not suitable according to the standard -due to the deformation being higher than half of the tank thickness-, a tank similar to Case 4 was selected for further analysis and design exploration (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Weight Maximum Deformation Comparison

Structural FE Analysis. In order to visualize the structures dictated by the EN 12573-3: 2000 standard the cases studied using calculations from the standard, were recreated in Ansys and were recalculated using the FEA approach. In Table 3 the dimensions of the tank for Case 4 are shown and in Figure 4 the deformation.

Table 3. Tank with Rim Stiffening and two (2) Intermediate Horizontal Stiffeners – Case 4

Internal Tank Dimensions	Length: 1220mm Width: 300mm Height: 840mm
Thickness	10 mm
Rim Reinforcements	L shaped 20 x 3 mm
Rib Reinforcements	2 Ribs L shaped 35 x 4 mm and 40 x 4 mm
Weight	41kg

Figure 4 Deformation for tank with Rim Stiffening and two (2) Intermediate Horizontal Stiffeners – Case 4.

As it is shown, the maximum deformation occurs on the side panels and more specific in the area between the two ribs. The maximum deformation using the normal Young Modulus equals 2.6 mm and for the long-term Young Modulus is 4.4 mm. For a tank thickness of 10 mm, the tank fulfills the standards requirements.

In consistency with the geometry of Case 4, modulations circumferentially to the tank, were constructed in order for the ribs and rim to be placed. A supplementary study was carried out in order to monitor how the stress and strains are affected by those modifications. Initially, a tank with 3 modulations was modeled, one lip for supporting the rim at the top of the tank and two modulations for the ribs. The modulated tank exhibited slightly larger deformations than the first design so parametric studies on the number of modulations and their position yielded the final, optimal tank geometry which incorporates one (1) ST-37 Rim on the top of the tank, two (2) ST 37 Ribs and 5 modulations (Figure 5).

Reinforcements

- Number of modulations: 5
- 1 Rim L shaped 20 x 3 mm, ST-37
- 2 Ribs L shaped 35 x 4 mm and 40 x 4 mm ST-37
- Weight: 55 kg

Figure 5 Case 4 redesigned – Addition of modulations – Final design

In order to reduce the weight of the tank, the rim and ribs only extend along the big panels of the tank and are held together with a threaded rod. This setup has minimum effect on the maximum deformation and still it is inside the acceptable deformation yielded from the EN 12573-3: 2000 standard. The final tank deformation is 2.6 mm using the normal Young modulus and 4.8 mm for the long-term Young Modulus both deformations are according to the standard. In order to insulate the tank with a uniform layer of insulation, the tank rests on two steel (ST37) feet screwed to the outer cover. Because of this arrangement max deformation occurred on the bottom of the tank and in the middle (Figure 6). To minimize the maximum bending moment, a parametric study was conducted in order to find the best position for placing the feet. The input parameter was the distance of the stands from the edge of the tank (x-axis) and the output parameter was the maximum deformation (y-axis). The stands were positioned symmetrically on the bottom of the plastic tank because of the evenly distributed load.

Figure 6 Final geometry with feet in the right position – Maximum deformation

Summarising, each tank consists of the plastic tank and its plastic lid, in which the heat exchanger is immersed in the

PCM. The geometry and dimensions of the plastic tank are the same for HTES, CTES and DHW applications. Each plastic tank has five modulations on its surface, one rim on top and three steel ribs for support. The heat exchanger is put on two steel feet on the bottom of the plastic tank so the HE and the plastic tank, are not in direct contact. The maximum deformation using the normal Young Modulus equals 2.8 mm and for the long-term Young Modulus is 4.6 mm. The values are according to the standard specification.

Thermal analysis. The thermal analysis is performed for the final geometry selected. The goal is to find the correct insulation thickness, in order to operate the tank with minimum thermal losses. It was found that for all applications 8cm of polyurethane should be applied to minimize heat losses. In Figure 7 typical results are shown for HTES tank considering two ambient temperatures 19°C and 25°C. The results of the thermal analysis showed that the maximum temperature on the surface of the tank is 29.65°C and 33.75°C for the cases of ambient temperatures 19°C and 25°C respectively, and it is observed, for both cases, on the bottom of the tank near the two steel feet. That is expected as the feet come in direct contact with the plastic container and the metal cover, so the insulation locally is thinner than the rest of the tank. The average temperatures on the surface of the tank is 21.55°C for the 19°C ambient temperature case and 27.05 for the 25°C ambient temperature. The results show adequate behavior of the insulation.

Figure 7 Tank with 8cm insulation - HTES conditions

The whole assembly (tank, ribs, feet, lid, and insulation) is placed inside a rectangular metal container (external cover) and on top of it the metal lid is placed (Figure 8). A protective resin coating is applied in the inner surface of the plastic tank to prevent mass uptake and degradation of the tank material. The tanks for the three applications were constructed based on the design presented above. They tested at laboratory [11,12] where it was confirmed that they meet the application requirements.

Figure 8 Tanks constructed according to the final design.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, typical results from the procedure followed to design TES tanks for certain applications HTES, CTES and DHW, are presented. The tanks for all applications have the same design. Using standards' guidelines, the concept tank design is developed and with FEA analysis parametric studies the geometry is defined concluding on

the number of modulations and their position yielded the final tank geometry which incorporates one (1) ST-37 Rim on the top of the tank, two (2) ST 37 Ribs and five (5) modulations. Each tank is insulated with an 8 cm thick polyurethane layer and is enclosed in a thin steel shell and its upper surface can be accessed through an insulated lid.

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